

Conversion of Thiochroman-4-one into the corresponding Spiro-thiazole and -pyrimidine Derivatives

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Reaction of cysteine and 2-aminothiophenol with thiochroman-4-one gives thiazoline and benzothiazoline derivatives 1 and 2, respectively. Thiochroman-4-one with bromine and thiourea forms 2-aminothiazole derivative (3). Thiochroman-4-one with urea and thiourea in the presence of benzaldehyde gives pyrimidine derivatives 4 and 5, respectively.

THIOCHROMANS and thiochroman-4-ones possess significant biological properties¹. Derivatives of thiazoles, benzothiazoles and pyrimidines form an integral part of a large number of therapeutically important compounds. Only a few examples are known in the literature for the synthesis of polycyclic systems from thiochroman-4-ones. This might be due to unsuccessful attempts in the preparation of derivatives of thiochroman-4-ones (by convenient methods) having suitable functional groups such as OH, NH₂, halogens, COOH, COOR and =CHR at position-C₃ (adjacent to the carbonyl function), necessary for ring closure reactions. This paper describes *in situ* functionalisation of C₃ with the reagents such as bromine and benzaldehyde to afford one-pot synthesis of polycyclic systems from thiochroman-4-one derivatives.

The thiazoline derivative (1) was obtained by treating thiochroman-4-one with cysteine. This reaction is based on the reaction of carbonyl compounds with 1,2-aminothiols to give thiazoline derivatives². The thiol and amine groups present on the adjacent carbon atoms in the cysteine molecule react with carbonyl group of thiochroman-4-one to form the spiro compound (1) bearing thiazoline ring system. 2-Aminothiophenol reacted with thiochroman-4-one in the same way as did cysteine to form another spiro compound (2) having benzothiazoline ring system³.

The most extensively used synthesis of thiazole derivatives involves the reaction between a thioamide and a halocarbonyl compound⁴. This synthesis has been further simplified by the use of carbonyl compound and bromine which are allowed to react *in situ* in the presence of the added amide⁵. In the present work, the thiazole derivative (3) was obtained by treating thiochroman-4-one with thiourea in presence of bromine. 3-Bromothiochroman-4-one appears to be the most probable intermediate in this reaction which reacts with thiourea to form the thiazole derivative (3).

The synthesis of the pyrimidine derivative from chroman-4-one has been reported earlier in the literature⁶. Thiochroman-4-one reacts in the same way as does chroman-4-one with benzaldehyde in presence of HCl gas in n-butanol to give *in situ* 3-benzyliden-chroman-4-one. Its reaction with urea and thiourea gave the pyrimidine derivatives 4 and 5, respectively.

The structure of compounds 1-5 has been established on the basis of N and S analyses, ir and pmr spectral data (Table 1). The reaction pathway has been outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (a) HSCH₂CH(COOH)NH₂, (b) 2-aminothiophenol, (c) Br₂, (d) C₆H₅CHO, dry HCl in n-butanol, (e) H₂NCSNH₂, (f) H₂NCONH₂.

TABLE 1—PMR SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	ArH	SCH ₂	CH ₂	CH	NH ₂
1	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS ₂	7.2–8.1 (4H, m)	4.25–4.50 (4H, m)	3.25–3.35 (2H, tr)	4.25–4.50–1H	—
2	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NS ₂	7.2–8.1 (8H, m)	4.25–4.35 (2H, tr)	3.25–3.35 (2H, tr)	—	—
3	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ S ₂	7.2–8.1 (4H, m)	4.40 (2H, s)	—	—	5.55 (2H, bd s) ^b
4	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	6.8–8.0 (9H, m)	4.40 (2H, s)	—	4.25 (s) ^a	—
5	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	6.8–8.0 (9H, m)	4.40 (2H, s)	—	4.25 (s) ^a	—

^aWith splitting 1H. ^bDisappeared on D₂O addition.

Cyclic NH merged in TFA

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian EM 390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and trifluoroacetic acid as the solvent. Purity of the compound was ascertained by tlc using 0.25 mm thick plates coated with silica gel G as stationary phase and two solvent systems, ethanol–benzene (1:5) and acetone–petroleum ether (1:5) as mobile phase. Elemental analyses of the compounds were found satisfactory.

2,2-[4-(1-Benzthiopyrano)]thiazoline-4-carboxylic acid (1): Treatment of thiochroman-4-one (1.476 g, 0.009 mol) with α -cysteine (1.160 g, 0.009 mol) at the reflux temperature for 3 h furnished a semi-solid mass which on cooling solidified on trituration with ether. Two fractions were separated in benzene from the crude product. The benzene-soluble fraction (A) yielded a solid crystallised from ethanol–benzene (20:80), (1; 1.63 g, 62.58%), m.p. 95°; R_f 0.68; system (a); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 680s, 1350s, 3400m, 1640m, 1720s, 1570s, 1430s and 2450w cm^{-1} . The second fraction (B) was not identified due to paucity of material.

2,2-[4-(1-Benzthiopyrano)]-2,3-benzothiazoline (2): Thiochroman-4-one (1.9680 g, 0.012 mol) was treated with 2-aminothiophenol (2.0 g, 0.016 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) at the reflux temperature for 2 h. The separated semi-solid mass was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to yield. The resulting yellow product was crystallised from ethanol, (2; 2.30 g, 70.78%), m.p. 105°; R_f 0.66; system (b); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 730vs, 1450s, 3450m and 1560m cm^{-1} .

2-Amino(1-benzthiopyrano)-(4,3-b)-thiazole (3): Thiochroman-4-one (1.9680 g, 0.012 mol) was treated with thiourea (0.9880 g, 0.013 mol) in the presence of bromine (1.5 ml) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) at 0.5°. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h and the completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc [system (a)]. The resulting crude product was crystallised from methanol to furnish 3 (1.26 g, 47.72%) (m.p. 175°); R_f 0.83; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 690s, 1610vs, 1550s, 3350m and 1200–1270w cm^{-1} .

4-Phenyl-5H-(1-benzthiopyrano)-(4,3-d)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-2-one (4): Thiochroman-4-one (1.312 g, 0.008 mol) reacted with benzaldehyde (0.972 g, 0.009 mol) and urea (0.480 g, 0.008 mol)

in butanol (10 ml) and dry HCl gas was passed slowly for 0.5 h to make the medium acidic. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h and the reaction was monitored by tlc [system (b)]. The semi-solid mass obtained after cooling was solidified on trituration with ether, and crystallised from petroleum ether to give 4 (0.92 g, 39.18%) (m.p. 104°); R_f 0.86; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 740s, 1640s, 1570s and 3400m cm^{-1} .

Similarly, 4-phenyl-5H-(1-benzthiopyrano)-(4,3-d)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-2-thione (5) was prepared by reacting thiochroman-4-one with benzaldehyde and thiourea in butanol and HCl gas, (53.23%) (m.p. 195°); R_f 0.21; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 690s, 1200s, 1570vs and 3400m cm^{-1} .

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